

FORMATION OF INDEPENDENT OBSERVATIONS OF SOIL SCIENCE TEACHING

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U.B.Mirzayev

, associate professor.

Fergana State University

Annotation.

The article presents analyzes of how to properly conduct their independent work at a high-quality level in the training of highly qualified soil scientists in technical schools, and gives recommendations based on the instructions for independent observation work.

Key words.

Independent observation, soil section, genetic layers, experiment, humus, accumulator, reconnaissance.

INTRODUCTION.

At present, special importance is attached to the formation of young people, who are the builders of society, into spiritually rich, morally mature, intellectually developed, highly educated and mature individuals.

One of the urgent problems of education in the teaching of soil science is the formation of the student's cognitive independence. It is of the utmost importance that students move from mastering the acquired knowledge to independent learning activities, taking into account the unique characteristics and capabilities of each student.

In the teaching of soil science, conducting scientific research and independent observations of students as a continuation of educational work creates great opportunities for them to receive systematic education and to develop their creative abilities.

From this point of view, in the module-credit system of education, special attention is paid to independent education and it is considered as the main foundation of the education system [1-5].

MAIN PART.

Recently, the science of soil science has been widely included in the secondary special education system. In this regard, it is necessary to develop separate

instructions for students to conduct independent work in order to deepen their education in this system.

Extracurricular independent educational activities for teaching soil science are diverse and, like other subjects, they are divided into three groups:

1. individual training;
2. group training;
3. public training.

Individual classes are conducted individually with some students who are interested in soil science.

Examples of such activities include reading scientific and popular books on soil science, studying the creative work of famous soil science scientists, studying the types and types of the soil of the place where one lives, determining the genetic layers by making a cross section of the soil, and explaining the description of the layers. . From plant science, autumn plowing of cotton lands, preparation of land and seed for planting, planting, working between rows of cotton, complete harvesting of seeds, harvesting, and measurement of the thickness of cotton bushes per hectare. In order to be successful, they carry out work such as determining how many plants to leave in one meter and working between cotton rows [6-10].

Conducting independent observations forms students' interest in learning, deepens their knowledge, increases their activity and teaches them to work independently. Most importantly, they develop skills and competences.

Independent individual observations are carried out in the educational field of the technical school or in the farm fields.

The content, purpose, procedure, and results of observation work are always recorded in a special diary. For example, earth cutting works are carried out in the following order. 1. Choosing a place for the soil section. Usually, it is carried out in farm fields. First, reconnaissance work is carried out. Then, a section of soil is placed on the designated area. The soil cross-section is placed until the seepage water comes out if the agricultural soil cover is in the hydromorphic zone, and if it is in the automorphic zone, it is placed up to the parent soil. Cutting is performed on the basis of existing accepted general guidelines.

2. At the next stage, the following are performed and they are formalized and recorded:

- Determination of upper layer A;
- Identifying the permeable layer;
- Determination of subsoil parent rock layers;

- depending on the development of soil formation processes, each layer can be divided into several layers, i.e. layer A is the forest understory layer; A1 humus accumulator layer; A2 observation of the division into wash or eluvial layer;
- Observation of the sum of layer A and V-soil thickness.
- C layer - to describe the soil parent rock and determine its type.

It is important for the student's activity, giving them specific assignments and the teacher's monitoring of their implementation for the complete completion of individual work outside of class [11-14].

It is important for students to read books and magazines in this field and make full use of current scientific and technical achievements in effectively conducting the above-mentioned extracurricular activities. In addition, independent observation of the analysis based on the comparison of the data in this regard with the data of foreign literature and recording in the notebook will give high results and will be the basis for future work.

At the end of the study, the students formalize the results. This process is performed at the expense of the camera period. The obtained information is summarized and relevant conclusions are formalized. They prepare presentations on research results.

CONCLUSION.

As a result of organizing independent observations in the above order, students will develop practical skills for the theoretical knowledge they have acquired. This form of training is a sample for independent observations, and it is recommended to organize other types of work in such forms. Classes organized in this way are of great practical importance in strengthening students' theoretical knowledge.

REERENCES:

1. Бегимкулов У.Ш. Педагогик таълим жараёнларини ахборотлаштиришни ташкил этиш ва бошқариш назарияси ва амалиёти: Педагогика фанлари доктори. ... дисс. – Т., 2007. – Б.3
2. Бегимкулов У.Ш. Педагогик таълимда замонавий ахборот технологияларини жорий этишнинг илмий назарий асослари.Т.; “Фан”, 2007.159 б.
3. Исаков В. Ю., Мирзаев У. Б., Юсупова М. А. Особенности характеристики почв песчаных массивов Ферганской долины //Научное обозрение. Биологические науки. – 2020. – №. 1. – С. 15-19.

4. Мирзаев У. Б., Умаркулова Б. Н. Влияние антропогенного фактора на эволюцию орошаемых арзык-шоховых почв //Научное обозрение. Биологические науки. – 2020. – №. 2. – С. 5-9.
5. Isakov V., Mirzaev U. Dynamics of arzyk-shokh meadow sasa soils under influence of irrigation //Scientific journal of the Fergana State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 47-50.
6. Исаков В. Ю., Мирзаев У. Б., Юсупова М. А. Гипсоносные почвы ферганской долины и их изменения под влиянием антропогена //Ученый XXI века. – 2017. – Т. 12.
7. Mirzaev U., Umarkulova B., Ganiev Y. Use of organic fertilizers, prepared from local waste, to improve the properties of meadow sulf soils: <https://doi.org/10.47100/conferences.v1i1.1340> //Research Support Center Conferences. – 2021. – №. 18.06.
8. Mirzayev U. B. Tuproqshunoslik” kursini o ‘qitishda pedagogik texnologiyalar. – 2023.
9. Mirzaev U. КОЛЛЕКТОР-ЗОВУРЛАР ТИЗИМИНИНГ ТУПРОҚДАГИ ТУЗЛАРНИНГ ҚАЙТА ТАҚСИМЛАНИШИДАГИ РОЛИ //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. D8. – С. 555-559.
10. Тожибоева Д. Махсус фанларни ўқитиш технологияси. Т.; Фан-техника ривожлантириш маркази. 2007.
11. Толипов Ў., Усмонбоева М. Педагогик технология: назария ва амалиёт. Т.; “Фан”, 2005.
12. Толипова Ж.О. Педагогик квалиметрия. Ўқув қўлланма. – Т.: ТДПУ, 2015.
13. Хайдаров, М. М. (2020). Основы применения гуминовых веществ в светлых сероземах. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(8), 87-93.
14. Юлдашев, Г. Х., & Хайдаров, М. М. (2021). Потенциальная энергия гумуса-критерия бонитировки почв. *Научное обозрение. Биологические науки*, (3), 11-15